

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most typical is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Can be dark or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not all the time black in coloration. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear will be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected beneath the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 toes in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of one of the best at climbing bushes. Their comparatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb bushes for protection, meals, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their food regimen is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Diet: Their assorted weight-reduction plan gives them the flexibility to dwell in a big vary of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They're the almost certainly bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are responsible for nearly all bear attacks in North America, with 46 per year. Although their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and reduced habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the identify of essentially the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals corresponding to elk and moose. Their colour varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred **big panda teddy** to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder top of 3. Three toes. □□ Food plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be larger than these found within the Rocky Mountains resulting from a richer diet. Each year there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Known for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are responsible for essentially the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are nearly as giant as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 ft long, and 4 toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight loss program: Their food regimen is much like mainland grizzly bears. However, as a result of more plentiful meals sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social construction which ends up in less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. As a result of their isolation, there is only one assault on people every other 12 months. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is usually made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the biggest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Measurement: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and might be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species attributable to loss of habitat from climate change. Regardless of their monumental measurement polar bears might be quick, sustaining a 6 mph pace in the water. □□ Features: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss plan: Their food plan consists principally of animals, particularly seals which they can smell from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears could be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are rare as a result of distant nature of their habitat. Known for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Simple to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account vulnerable. □□ Measurement: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand 47 to 75 inches tall. □□ Diet: Relying on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and

honey. Attacks on humans are increasing as people encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently common in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its food regimen is bamboo. In fact, the second person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while protecting his sheep. Known for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 remain in the wild and they're considered a vulnerable species. ☐☐ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over 4 toes tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at birth. It additionally has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in gentle brown and white. ☐☐ Food regimen: Not like different bears the panda's weight loss plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over 40 times a day! ☐☐ Harmful? Attacks are rare but dangerous, provided that pandas have considered one of the best chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought of vulnerable and on the decline as a result of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body parts utilized in traditional medicines. ☐☐ Dimension: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They're named for his or her pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that appears like a rising sun. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Sun bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." The truth is, they have an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Harmful? Attributable to its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they are thought of weak. ☐☐ Size: They're 55 to seventy five inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they are easy to inform apart from different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very quick and might out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from trees. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Weight loss plan: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Harmful? They are one of the aggressive bears, with essentially the most assaults on people, largely because of surprise encounters. They blow the dust round with massive puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and do not combine well with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final quick-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that appear to be glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Measurement: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final brief-faced bear and the one bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in trees where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Eating regimen: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a food regimen consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Harmful? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears often is the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears but larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA checks have been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas usually are not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in space. Most bear attacks happen when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their very own household that are nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.

Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is close by, in which case you wish to be further vigilant. Listed below are a few ideas you should use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure.

2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are here so they do not by chance startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have nice intentions, a bear is more likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** In case you see a bear, do not try to strategy or feed it. This contains food, but in addition your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, be sure it's a minimum of 200 toes away out of your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite.
4. **Stay CALM.** Should you meet a bear, don't run. Attempt to make yourself look as large as doable, waving your arms above your head. You can too prolong a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or attempt to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.
6. **Combat Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play lifeless. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet long, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the biggest bear by each measurement and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat again with all your strength and hope that it will back down. Which bear is probably the most harmful? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for probably the most assaults. When in bear country, it's at all times wise to hold bear spray. It's properly deserved, especially when cubs are around. Every year there are approximately forty six grizzly attacks, 6 leading to demise. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome popularity. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per yr. In terms of raw bite energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and not to be messed with. When utilizing the bite power quotient (chunk energy relative to measurement), the solar bear packs essentially the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he turned an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-working public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous thru-hikers to try and master the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free lifestyle. He also could be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son often would go to at the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada close to where he was from. Chris also wrote How to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal components backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

